

THE AMYLASE ACTIVITY OF SWEET CASSAVA (*MANIHOT PALMATA*).

BY K. S. MURTY.

In view of the lack of knowledge regarding the amylolytic enzymes of tubers, the amylase activity of sweet cassava has been studied. The results obtained will be of considerable interest in the manufacture of starch from cassava.

In view of our meagre knowledge of the amylase activity of tubers it was thought desirable to investigate the amylase from cassava (*Manihot Palmata*). Cassava is widely cultivated in the tropics. Its mineral requirements being very low, it is particularly well adopted for cultivation on poor sandy soils. The yield on a well irrigated land may amount to 15—16 tons per acre. According to the analysis of Leuscher (*Offentl. Chem.* 1902, 8, 10) the fresh tuber contains water (70.25%), protein (1.12%), fat (0.41%), starch (21.44%), sugar (5.13%), crude fibre (1.11%), and ash (0.54%).

There are two varieties of cassava tubers, the sweet and the bitter. Francis (*Analyst*, 1878, 2, 4) found 0.0168% of hydrocyanic acid in the sweet cassava (*Manihot palmata*) root and 0.0275% in the bitter cassava (*Manihot utilissima*) root. Cellens (*Bull. Dept. Agric., Trinidad and Tobago*, 1915, 14, 54) found 0.0048% of hydrocyanic acid in the roots of the sweet variety and 0.0053% in the roots of the bitter variety. The leaves and the stems also contain hydrocyanic acid. The leaves of the sweet and the bitter varieties contain 0.0162% and 0.041% of hydrocyanic acid respectively and the peelings of the stems 0.043% and 0.113% respectively.

It will be seen from the above analysis that cassava contains a very high percentage of starch and very low percentage of mineral matter. It should, therefore, prove particularly valuable for the manufacture of starch.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Fresh tubers of the sweet variety were obtained direct from the fields. The thick outer skin was removed and the skinned tuber was chopped into very thin slices, which were dried in the sun, powdered and sieved. The powder could be well preserved in bottles, for considerable length of time without any deterioration.

Preparation of the Enzyme Extract.—60 G. of the powder were ground into a thin paste with about four times the quantity (250 c.c.) of water. This was transferred into an Erlenmeyer flask and toluene (2-3 c.c.) was added to avoid bacterial action thereby preventing a fall in the activity of the enzyme. This was kept for 24 hours and the clear liquid above was decanted into a separate flask. This was used for subsequent work.

Method of Procedure.—Pure soluble starch (Schering) was used as the substrate. The hydrogen ion concentration of the reaction medium was adjusted by the addition of Sørensen's phosphate buffers for p_H values 5.6 to 8.0 and Walpole's acetate buffers for p_H values 3.0 to 5.0. Enzyme extract was prepared (as described above) afresh for each experiment.

The experiments were carried out in Erlenmeyer flasks. Controls were set up for each experiment with starch alone, without the addition of the enzyme. After hydrolysis, the maltose formed was estimated by the iodometric method of Willstätter and Schüdel (*Ber.*, 1918, 41, 780).

Influence of Temperature on the Enzyme Activity.—The activity of the enzyme was studied at temperatures varying from 30°-70° at intervals of 5°. The p_H of the buffer used was 6.8. Each experiment consisted of a set of two flasks (referred to in the table as I and II).

I. Enzyme and starch.		II. Starch alone.	
2.5% Starch soln.	9 c.c.	2.5% Starch soln.	9 c.c.
Buffer soln.	5 c.c.	Buffer soln.	5 c.c.
Enzyme extract	1 c.c.	Water	1 c.c.

TABLE I.

Temp. ($\pm 0.1^\circ$).	Maltose formed in 30 minutes.		Temp. ($\pm 0.1^\circ$).	Maltose formed in 30 minutes	
30°	24.0 mg.	18.0 mg.	50°	24.9 mg.	21.0 mg.
35°	24.0	18.8	55°	27.6	21.2
40°	24.9	18.8	60°	26.7	21.2
45°	24.9	20.6	70°	26.6	21.2

From the above results it is evident that the optimum temperature for the enzyme activity is about 55°.

Influence of p_H on the Enzyme Activity.—Hydrogen ion concentrations varying from p_H 3 to 8 were studied at intervals of about 0.5. The temperature was maintained throughout the course of the experiment at

30°. Controls were set up as in the previous experiment and the results obtained are given in mg. of maltose formed in 30 minutes.

TABLE II.

p_H	I.	II.	p_H	I.	II.
3.0	24.8 mg.	21.2 mg.	6.2	25.8 mg.	18.0 mg.
3.8	24.9	21.2	6.5	27.5	18.8
4.4	24.9	21.2	6.7	25.8	18.8
5.0	25.7	18.0	7.0	25.7	18.9
5.6	25.8	17.1	7.4	24.0	20.6
5.9	25.8	17.2	8.0	24.0	23.2

It is evident from the above results that the optimum p_H for the enzyme activity is about 6.5.

The author desires to express his indebtedness to Dr. G. Gopala Rao of the University College, Waltair, for suggesting the problem. He also thanks Dr. K. V. Giri of the Andhra University, Waltair, and Mr. P. V. Krishna Murty of the Andhra Medical College, Vizagapatam, for their kind encouragement.

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
ANDHRA MEDICAL COLLEGE,
VIZAGAPATAM.

Received May 25, 1940.